

DEVELOPING A HEALTHY DIET PLAN FOR YOUNG ATHLETES

G. Kh. Abdumalikova, N.M. Ibrogimova ,
Uzbek State University of Physical
Education and Sports

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы питания юных спортсменов, учитывая воздействие физических нагрузок, процессы роста и развития сбалансированности рационов по важнейшим пищевым факторам, а также говорится об особенностях рациона питания спортсмена и необходимости модифицирования питания спортсменов в зависимости от спортивной специализации в связи со специфичностью биохимической адаптации организма к мышечной деятельности, обусловленной ее характером и интенсивностью.

Ключевые слова: юные спортсмены, интенсивная мышечная деятельность, сбалансированный рацион, биологическая ценность.

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the nutritional issues of young athletes, taking into account the impact of physical activity, the processes of growth and development of a balanced diet for the most important nutritional factors, and also talks about the characteristics of the athlete's diet and the need to modify the nutrition of athletes depending on sports specialization in connection with the specificity of the biochemical adaptation of the body to muscle activity, due to its nature and intensity.

Keywords: young athletes, intense muscular activity, balanced diet, biological value.

INTRODUCTION.

Ensuring proper nutrition for young athletes is crucial for their growth, development, and athletic performance. A well-balanced diet provides the necessary energy and nutrients to support rigorous training, enhance recovery, and maintain overall health. Here are the key principles and recommendations for organizing proper nutrition for young athletes.

Balance of Macronutrients: Proteins Essential for muscle growth and tissue repair. Sources include lean meats, fish, eggs, dairy products, and legumes.

Fats: Important for energy and cellular functions. Healthy sources are fish, nuts, seeds, and plant oils.

- Carbohydrates: The primary source of energy. Opt for whole grains, vegetables, fruits, and legumes.

Regular Meals: Consistent meal timing helps maintain energy levels and prevents overeating. Aim for three main meals and 2-3 snacks daily.

Hydration: Adequate hydration is vital before, during, and after training sessions. Water is the best choice, while sugary and carbonated drinks should be limited.

Vitamins and Minerals: A varied diet rich in fruits and vegetables ensures an adequate intake of essential vitamins and minerals.

Intense muscular activity causes significant activation of metabolic processes in the body, which is associated with an increase in energy resources, increased processes of oxidative and anaerobic synthesis of energy-rich phosphorus compounds, increased biosynthesis of contractile muscle proteins and enzymes, improved regulation of metabolism, and naturally, the athlete's nutrition has its own peculiarities. The diet of athletes is characterized by increased caloric content, high levels of protein, fat, carbohydrates, mineral elements, vitamins, as well as features in the relationships between the main components of food. Due to the specificity of the body's biochemical adaptation to muscular activity, determined by its nature and intensity, the nutrition of athletes should be modified depending on their sports specialization. The choice of adequate forms of nutrition: selection of an appropriate assortment of products, the correct diet in accordance with the training regimen, the use of specialized products of increased biological value contributes to the creation of an optimal metabolic background in the pre-competition period, maintaining a high level of performance during the competition, activation of recovery processes during the rest period after physical exercise loads. Nutrition issues are of particular relevance in the practice of children's and youth sports, since here it is necessary to simultaneously take into account both the impact of physical activity on the body and the natural processes of growth and development. An important role in the rationalization of nutrition also belongs to the qualitative composition of nutrients and the balance of diets according to the most important nutritional factors - proteins, fats, carbohydrates, vitamins and minerals.

METHODOLOGY.

In the nutrition of children and adolescents, the protein part of the diet is especially important. The need for protein especially increases during training periods

associated with the development of qualities such as strength, speed, increased muscle mass, as well as when performing long-term and strenuous physical activity. To provide children and adolescents with a complete set of amino acids, the content of animal protein should be at least 60% of the total amount of protein in the diet. The main sources of complete animal protein are meat, offal, fish, poultry, cottage cheese, cheese, eggs, milk, and yogurt.

The fat content in the daily diet of young athletes should account for 28-30% of the total calorie content of food. The biological value of fats largely depends on the content of these fatty acids, which are among the essential nutritional factors. About 20-25% of all food fats should be replenished from vegetable fats.

RESULTS.

Carbohydrate metabolism in children is characterized by high intensity. When performing muscular work, carbohydrates are used as the main and most beneficial source of energy, due to their ability to be oxidized both in the presence of oxygen and without it. The child's body does not have the ability to quickly mobilize its internal carbohydrate resources and maintain the required intensity of carbohydrate metabolism when performing physical work. When playing sports, the need for carbohydrates increases significantly and is largely determined by the intensity of physical activity. Sources of carbohydrates are bread, flour, cereals, pasta, potatoes, sugar, confectionery, vegetables, fruits, berries. It is recommended that the bulk of carbohydrates, 65-70%, be administered with food in the form of polysaccharides, 25-30% should be simple and easily digestible carbohydrates. In a growing organism, the process of assimilation predominates, which is greatly influenced by vitamins, as regulators of all metabolic processes. The action of vitamins in various transformations of carbohydrates, fats and essential amino acids.

DISCUSSION.

Vitamins are almost never synthesized in the body on their own, and therefore it is especially important to monitor their intake from food. A lack of vitamins in the diet has a negative impact on the general state of metabolism and performance of young athletes. Vitamin A is found in liver, eggs, caviar, butter, milk, sour cream, cream, carrots, tomatoes, lettuce, and sorrel. Sources of vitamin B1 include mainly meat, offal, nuts, raisins, green peas, cereals and wholemeal baked goods. The highest content of vitamin B2 is observed in meat, milk, cottage cheese, cheese, liver, eggs, cereals, potatoes, cabbage, carrots, peas, and yeast. Vitamin C is found mainly in plant foods. Especially noteworthy are rose hips, black currants, fresh herbs, tangerines, lemons, sour apples, and cabbage.

CONCLUSION.

Proper nutrition is not only the key to athletic success but also the foundation for the overall health and well-being of young athletes. By following these guidelines, parents and coaches can help young athletes reach their full potential both on and off the field. The organization of nutrition for athletes during intense physical activity at different stages of preparation and especially during competitions involves the use of products of increased biological value, which are intended to have a targeted effect on the metabolism in the body, both during physical activity and during the rest period after them. In conclusion, we consider it necessary to once again emphasize that the rational construction of the training process in young athletes and increasing its effectiveness is only possible if the energy expenditure of the athletes corresponds to an optimally composed daily food ration, which includes all the essential nutritional component.

REFERENCES

1. Kurganovich, E. A., Anvarovich, E. S., Abdullayevich, Y. G., Xasanovich, U. X., Axtamkulovich, K. X., & Abdullayevna, Y. M. (2020). The distribution of training load among promising young gymnasts during the periods of the annual cycle. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(13), 1005-1007.
2. Ганиева, М. Ю., Фозилов, Х. К., & Муминов, А. Ш. (2019). Методы и средства развития и совершенствования силовых качеств гандболистов. In *Актуальные проблемы физической культуры и спорта* (pp. 147-149). 10. Сивохин, И. П., Огиенко, Н. А., Бекмухамбетова, Л. С., & Маткаримов, Р. М. (2019). Биомеханические аспекты совершенствования двигательных действий в спорте.
3. Khodjaev, A. Z. (2018). Improving Jerk Technique by Special-Auxiliary Exercises. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, 19-26. 12. Arzikulov, M. U. (2018). Distributing Parameters of Training Loading and Reduced Funds for Preparing Weightlifter at Stage of Sports Improvement. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, 14-18.
4. Makhmudov, K. (2020). Ways of Forming Intercultural Communication in Foreign Language Teaching. *Science and Education*, 1(4).
5. Makhmudov, K. (2020). Innovative Cluster of Pedagogical Education: Common Goals and Specific Interests. *Academic Research in Educational Sciences*, (2).